

**Significantly overestimated mobility and other inconsistencies in
A. Liu *et al.*, *Nature* 629, 798 (2024).**

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QUICK SUMMARY:

Analysis of device characteristics reported by A. Liu *et al.* [1] for Se-alloyed Te-TeO_x thin-film transistors (TFTs) reveals that:

- (1)** Different figures (and even different curves) corresponding to the same TFT yield widely different carrier mobilities μ , most of which turn out to be significantly smaller than the mobility reported by the authors.
- (2)** The output characteristics of the best optimized TFT yield field-effect mobilities that are at least twice smaller than that reported by the authors for this device (the mobility from the actual data is 6 - 7.5 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹, while the claimed mobility is 15 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹).
- (3)** It is shown here that the best TFT, which is said to have the record-high mobility of 15 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹, is actually not a well-behaved field-effect transistor (FET). This might partially explain the erroneous mobility and other significant inconsistencies occurred during the measurements and analysis of this device with the FET model suitable only for well-behaved FETs.
- (4)** It is also shown here that the reported optimized TFT actually exhibits very large hysteresis and nonlinearities, confirming that it cannot be regarded as a reliable, well-behaved transistor.
- (5)** Additional issues were discovered by readers and reported at *PubPeer*, including, for instance, false statements regarding the statistical plots included in the original paper and multiple duplicated identical curves that were supposed to represent physically different devices [2].
- (6)** The reported *on/off* current ratio for the optimized TFT appears to be severely miscalculated (inflated) by at least two orders of magnitude. The inflated *on/off* ratio is presented in this paper as a record breaking achievement.
- (7)** Finally, other serious issues were found by examining the [Peer Review](#) file of this paper available at *Nature*. For instance, it appears that the authors have provided misleading information to the Reviewers regarding the performance of their TFTs on thin HfO₂ gate dielectric. In addition, on several occasions, they seemed to have promised inclusion of important

additional data/information requested by the Reviewers, which, however, cannot be found in the published paper. The details are available at *PubPeer* [2].

TFT parameters stated in the paper: $L = 250 \mu\text{m}$, $W = 1000 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{\text{SiO}_2} = 100 \text{ nm}$ (i.e., the gate-channel capacitance per unit area is $C_i = 34.5 \text{ nF/cm}^2$).

Key Figures related to the characteristics of the optimized TFT: Fig. 3a (solid red line) and Fig. 3b (solid red lines) representing the transfer and output characteristics, respectively, of the best (optimized) TFT device. The mobility of this TFT is claimed to be $\mu_{\text{claimed}} = 15 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

ANALYSIS DETAILS:

1. The TFT mobility extracted from the output characteristics (Fig. 3b) in the *saturation* regime (green dots in the Figure below) turns out to be much smaller than μ claimed by the authors:

$$\mu_{\text{from-data-1}} \sim 6.0 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}.$$

2. The more comprehensive way to extract the mobility of a TFT is to perform the *global fit* (a fit using the data from all the curves) of the output characteristics of the device with the Shockley FET model (see, e.g., Refs. [3, 4] for the basic model description). Such a fit of the data in Fig. 3b is shown below (performed in Origin Pro 2024b). It yields the mobility:

$$\mu_{\text{from-data-2}} \sim 7.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1},$$

which is close to $\mu_{\text{from-data-1}}$ above, but is much smaller than $\mu_{\text{claimed}} = 15 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ reported by the authors. The Figure below shows this analysis, with the digitized data (left panel) and the global fit (right panel). On the right panel, dots are the digitized data, and the solid lines are the global fit by the Shockley FET model. Importantly, the mobilities, $\mu_{\text{from-data-1}}$ and $\mu_{\text{from-data-2}}$, obtained from these output characteristics significantly disagree (by a factor of $\sim 2 - 2.5$) with the mobility estimated by fitting the transfer curve (the red curve in Fig. 3a) with the same model. This disagreement clearly shows that there is an internal contradiction between these two pieces of data (Figs. 3a and 3b) representing the optimized TFT device.

Attempts to fit individual output curves *separately* yield widely varied mobilities that are all smaller than the claimed mobility, with the threshold voltages that not only differ from curve to curve but also strongly disagree with the threshold voltage of the transfer curve in Fig. 3a. In other words, the collection of output curves in Fig. 3b cannot be fitted with the same model to simultaneously obtain the reported mobility and the reported threshold voltage (regardless of the model used). The fact that the fit for the purple curve in the Figure below (at $V_{\text{GS}} = -40 \text{ V}$) is relatively poor does not mean that the fit is non-optimal, as this is a highly optimized best fit one can possibly get with the standard Shockley FET model (Refs. [3, 4]), given the published data in Fig. 3b. It simply proves our point that the device is not a well-behaved FET.

3. Re-plotting the transfer characteristic of the best TFT (Fig. 3a, red curve) on the double-linear plot reveals a very significant hysteresis and nonlinearities (see Figure below), showing that this is not a reliable, well-behaved FET. Such a high hysteresis also contradicts to the small bias stress effect alluded to by the authors in Fig. 3 d, e.

4. The obvious disagreement between the transfer and output TFT characteristics described above is concerning. Indeed, in a properly operating FET (or TFT), the transfer and output characteristics should lead to approximately the same mobility, as the same device model (the Shockley MOSFET model (Refs. [3,4])) describes all these curves, and the mobility μ in this model is a common fixed parameter. Irrespective of the carrier mobility, well-behaved FETs (that is, not physically defective devices) should operate in accordance with the Shockley model, which is built on a set of basic assumptions, including a carrier-density independent mobility. This model is equally applicable to TFTs based on high- μ crystalline and low- μ non-crystalline semiconductors, as long as those basic assumptions hold. In disordered (even amorphous) materials, it usually also works, because the maximum modulation of the carrier density in TFTs is still small compared to the density of relevant (semi)localized states. Furthermore, the mobility extraction from output characteristics of TFTs can utilize either the linear or the saturation regimes featured in these characteristics, or it can be based on a more comprehensive global fit of all the curves together, encompassing both the linear and saturation regimes simultaneously (as shown above). Of course, the mobility can also be extracted from the transfer characteristics of a TFT. Importantly, in a properly working TFT, there must be a consistency between the mobilities obtained by all these methods and in both the regimes (linear and saturation). Only when this is the case, one can state that the device is a well-behaved FET (TFT) that can be used for a reliable mobility reporting.

In principle, there is nothing complicated about fitting the output characteristics using the global fit, as it is essentially based on the same model/equations as any other method of mobility extraction in TFTs. For example, a similar analysis has been used in the past for organic FETs [5].

Since a significant mismatch is discovered between μ extracted from the output and transfer characteristics, we must say that the reported optimized TFT does not behave as a proper FET. In such a case, only the lowest extracted value of μ can be used as a quoted estimate for the charge carrier mobility of the system. However, even if such a conservative mobility reporting were

exercised by the authors, they still should have investigated possible causes of the abnormal device behavior and provided a justification for applying the existing FET models developed for well-behaved FETs. We found no such discussion in the paper.

In addition, the mobility in this paper was estimated from a single curve (the transfer curve in Fig. 3a, red solid line) and without properly reporting the measurement conditions. Overwhelming evidence indicates that such an approach typically leads to unreliable conclusions, especially when applied to non-linear/high-hysteresis devices, thus leading to significantly inflated TFT mobilities (see, e.g., recent analysis of a series of problematic papers [6-11]).

More specifically, in poorly-behaving TFTs such as those reported in this paper, their parameters might significantly depend on such factors as measurement speed, the magnitude of the source-drain voltage, heat dissipation and others. Thus, with such devices, estimating the mobility from a single transfer curve (recorded at one voltage sweep rate, and in one operation regime) would very likely lead to an erroneous result. Even in a seemingly well-behaved FET, the mobility can be easily overestimated, for instance, by sweeping the gate voltage at a too high rate while recording the device characteristics [12]. The authors of Ref. [1] have not reported any sweep-rate dependence of their mobility.

Furthermore, using the rather common derivative-based method of mobility extraction in non-linear poorly-behaving TFTs has been proven dangerous. It is well known in the community to frequently lead to overestimated mobilities [6,13].

To summarize this section, A. Liu *et al.* (Ref. [1]) report a mobility extracted from a single curve recorded at a single set of device operation parameters, which is unreliable. On top of that, as shown in sections 1-3 above, the reported mobility contradicts the mobility extracted from the other FET characteristics shown in the paper (yielding significantly smaller μ). This suggests that the mobility reported in this paper is inflated considerably.

5. It appears that there are multiple issues within the [Peer Review](#) file downloadable from *Nature*. For instance, the mobility of a TFT device with 40 nm-thick HfO₂ gate dielectric, given by the authors to the Reviewers while answering their questions, turns out to be significantly inflated (by a factor of 5 - 20).

In the [Peer Review](#) file, while answering Q7 of Reviewer-3 (pages 19-20) and Q4 of Reviewer-4 (page 22) regarding the characteristics of TFTs with HfO₂ gate dielectric, the authors show data for a TFT with an ALD-grown 40 nm-thick HfO₂ gate dielectric, stating that the mobility of this device is 10 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (**Figures R13 and R16** of the [Peer Review](#) file):

R3Q7. In the section device fabrication, it is written that 100-nm thermally grown SiO₂ was used. However, the TFTs for the logic gates have been made on HfO₂ as gate dielectric. Please make this clear in the text and in the (caption of the) figures. Applying 40 V on this high-k dielectric implies a very large field. The same comment holds for comment (2): how does it scale down, as HfO₂ should enable much lower supply voltage operation, closer to the specifications of the applications. In addition, the characteristics of both TFTs are missing when characterized on HfO₂, which may have a large impact on V_t, on/off ratios and mobilities.

the individual TFT data. It was a bit of a pity. But, during the earlier device optimization before the final integration, we did some TFTs on 40-nm HfO₂, which showed good TFT character at a lower operation voltage of less than 10 V (shown below). In future work, more systematic studies on the dielectric effect

R4Q4. The authors claim to have demonstrated manufacturability, but the devices they make are on Si/SiO₂ wafers, rather than using large area technology with a deposited dielectric. While their approach is sufficient for a first publication, any further information they can give about the properties of their TFTs on a deposited oxide would be very valuable.

gate electrodes. The good circuit performance indicates the feasibility of TeO_x on a deposited dielectric. We also provide below a transfer curve of a TeO_x:Se TFT on ALD HfO₂, showing a μ_{th} of $\sim 10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and an I_{on}/I_{off} of $\sim 10^5$. The use of different dielectric layers may influence the channel layer growth and

Figure R13. Transfer curve of one TeO_x:Se TFT on a 40-nm ALD HfO₂ gate dielectric.

As shown in the analysis below, this mobility appears to be significantly overestimated. The actual mobility of this device (calculated by any possible approach) is 5 - 20 times smaller than $10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ pitched by the authors to the Reviewers.

Below is the analysis of the transfer curve of this TFT (green solid circles are the digitized data). Two possible sets of the channel width, W , and length, L , used by the authors in the paper were used here for the mobility calculations (either $L/W = 250/1000$ as in TFTs in Fig. 3, or $L/W = 60/100$ as in devices in Fig. 4). The correct capacitance per unit area for a 40 nm-thick HfO₂ is $C_i = 553 \text{ nF/cm}^2$ (the static dielectric constant of ALD-grown HfO₂ is $\epsilon = 25$ (see, e.g., Ref. [14]).

Furthermore, if one resorts to extracting the mobility by the so-called “derivative method”, it also turns out to be significantly lower than that claimed by the authors (even if one picks the maximum value corresponding to the spike in the derivative, which, of course, has nothing to do with the actual mobility). Strictly speaking, this method of mobility extraction is not applicable to TFTs with a non-linear transconductance behavior (non-linear $|I_{DS}|^{1/2}(V_{GS})$ in the saturation regime, and non-linear $I_{DS}(V_{GS})$ in the linear regime), such as this device, as it may lead to erroneous mobilities. Nevertheless, we apply it below just to check the numbers, again with the two possible sets of L and W used by the authors in this paper, and list the resultant mobility values averaged over the transistor’s ON state:

From this analysis, one can see that no matter how you calculate the mobility for this TFT, it is certainly going to be significantly smaller than the stated $10 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. A safe estimate for the mobility of this TFT would be:

$$\mu_{actual} \sim 0.84 - 2 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}.$$

Besides the crudely over-inflated mobility, it is also apparent from the replotted of the transfer curve on a double-linear scale (green solid symbols above) that this device also behaves poorly as a FET (TFT), which again contradicts to the statement given by the authors to the Reviewers at the stage of the peer review. The significance of this is that all this misleading information was apparently used (at least, in part) in the process of convincing the Reviewers.

CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion, the analysis of A. Liu *et al.* [1] reveals the following:

(1) The best (optimized) TFTs reported by the authors are not well-behaved field-effect transistors, thus requiring extreme care while extracting the carrier mobility by (any) established FET models. In particular, using a single curve for reporting the record μ is certainly unreliable and would bear little meaning, even if the dataset presented by the authors were not self-contradictory.

(2) The transistor dataset presented by the authors is significantly self-contradictory. Errors might have occurred in the course of the reported measurements or during data plotting, yielding inconsistent and self-contradictory results, with the reported TFT mobility that appears to be overestimated by at least a factor of two.

(3) More tricky issues are found in the [Peer Review](#) file downloadable from *Nature*. For instance, it appears that the authors have significantly misled the Reviewers regarding the performance of TFT devices on HfO₂ dielectric and left some of the promised data/information undisclosed. For details see *PubPeer* [2].

(4) Additional issues were discovered by readers and reported at *PubPeer*, including, for instance, false statements regarding the statistical plots included in the original paper and multiple duplicated identical curves that are supposed to represent different devices [2].

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